

THE MAIN FACILITIES AND METHODS OF PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract. *The school setting provides a promising environment to increase children's physical activity (PA), however, staff often impact the success of PA within schools. The purpose of this article was to describe the knowledge of elementary school staff related to PA and their perception of the importance of the school environment being conducive to PA prior to the implementation of a recess intervention.*

Keywords: *physical activity, perception, punishment, factors, method.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ СРЕДСТВА И МЕТОДЫ ФИЗИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ МЛАДШИХ ШКОЛЬНИКОВ

Аннотация. *Школьная обстановка обеспечивает многообещающую среду для повышения физической активности детей (ФА), однако персонал часто влияет на успех ФА в школах. Цель этой статьи состояла в том, чтобы описать знания персонала начальной школы, связанные с РА, и их восприятие важности школьной среды, способствующей РА до реализации вмешательства на перемене.*

Ключевые слова: *физическая активность, восприятие, наказание, факторы, метод.*

INTRODUCTION

For children of primary school age, the need for high physical activity is natural. With the transition from preschool education to systematic instruction in school for children 6-7 years old, the amount of physical activity is reduced by 50%.

The health status of our children is poor. Doctors say that absolutely healthy children among those entering the first grade are no more than 20 percent. The health of schoolchildren worsens as they grow older: malnutrition, stress, and lack of movement become the cause of the most common diseases among schoolchildren - diseases of the digestive system, kidneys, nervous and endocrine systems, as well as metabolism and the immune system.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

School is a huge burden on the fragile musculoskeletal system: a heavy satchel, a long motionless posture, a lack of active games, and sometimes emotional problems that make the child stoop, lead to impaired posture.

Physical education and sport, as you know, effectively contribute to the formation of a healthy lifestyle, including the implementation of personal hygiene rules, and daily routine, and the organization of a balanced diet. Therefore, it is important to start the physical education of the child in a timely manner.[3]

At a primary school age, the foundations of a person's physical culture are laid, interests, motivations and needs for systematic physical activity are formed. This age is especially favorable for mastering the basic components of the culture of movement, the development of an extensive arsenal of motor coordination, the technique of various physical exercises.

RESULTS

One of the basic requirements for the modern lesson is the introduction of effective means and methods of physical education. With their help, educational and developmental tasks are more successfully solved; provides a differentiated approach to students, the adequacy of physical activity to their physical condition; sustained interest in classes.

Each lesson should be correctly structured and content and comprehensively solve problems associated with studying the basics of knowledge of physical culture, mastering motor skills, developing physical qualities, mastering the skills to independently engage in physical exercises, instilling the need for a healthy lifestyle.[1]

The impact of each lesson on students should be diverse. The physical, mental and volitional efforts of children should be combined in such a way that, on the whole, the effect of harmonious development of students is ensured while maintaining the optimal level of their performance. Therefore, difficult exercises should be combined with relatively easy ones, interesting ones - with boring, but necessary, obligatory ones - with exercises for choosing children, etc.

In the process of physical education, it is necessary, whenever possible, to provide an individual approach to students, taking into account the state of their health, physical development, gender and physical fitness.

With a group method, a class is divided into groups. Each of the groups performs its own task, which differs from the others. The group method provides a differentiated approach to students in the learning process movements. The teacher selects exercises that correspond to the strengths and abilities of the group members.

DISCUSSION

The use of the group method makes it possible to accustom children to independent physical exercises. If the students are not adequately prepared for this form of organization of classes, it is impractical to use the group method.

The method of individual lessons involves the independent implementation of exercises proposed by the teacher or selected by the students. It is used in the preparatory or main part of the lesson, but can also take place in the final.

The method of individual lessons makes it possible to satisfy the desire of students to complete their favorite exercise. As a result, there is an alternation of regulated exercises with relatively free ones. However, children are accustomed to independent exercise. At the same time, the teacher, observing individual students, exercises overall leadership of the class.

The method of additional exercises. Additional are called exercises that are performed on the instructions of the teacher independently in conjunction with the main exercise. However, additional exercises cannot be considered secondary, since thanks to them, it is possible to develop the physical qualities of younger students. The essence of this technique is that, in addition to the main exercise, which students perform in turn, in the intervals between approaches, they perform the proposed number of times exercises aimed at developing certain physical qualities.[2]

Station occupation method. Station lessons are a kind of circular training aimed mainly at consolidating and improving motor skills.

The essence of this form of training is as follows. The class is divided into several groups so that in each group there are no more than 3-5 people. Groups disperse at the stations indicated by the teacher. At the signal of the teacher, all students at the same time begin to perform exercises each in their place. After completing the exercise, a predetermined number of times, the groups clockwise move to the next place of employment. And so on, until all the training places have been completed.

The circular method of employment. The movement of students occurs, as in station classes, in a circle with the sequential execution of exercises at each place.

However, in contrast to the station, the round-robin classes are mainly aimed at the development of physical qualities, and here new, increased requirements are presented to the students: to repeat a given exercise as many times as possible or to perform a given amount as quickly as possible.

Traditionally considered the most important means of physical education of students. These exercises to the greatest extent ensure their general physical fitness, and is also an indispensable school of motor culture, because forms in children the ability to control their movements in a coordinated, precise, beautiful way.[1]

A huge variety of exercises related to gymnastics, allows you to successfully solve educational, health and educational tasks. Any gymnastics exercise can be easily dosed according to the main load parameters. Therefore, she has great pedagogical capabilities. A teacher of school physical education, who has not mastered perfectly the basics of the gymnastic method, significantly impoverishes his pedagogical skills and thereby his students.

CONCLUSIONS

The daily routine may not be the same for everyone. It differentiates depending on the state of health, level of performance, specific living conditions and individual characteristics of students. But there are a number of rules that are mandatory for everyone. Common and common for all students should be such regimen moments as morning exercises, a toilet, school classes, lunch, afternoon breaks, homework, community service, outdoor activities, sports, hobbies, moderate attendance at entertainment events , dinner, evening walk, preparation for bed.

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